

Identifying Students' Perceptions on YouTube Media in English Learning for Meeting, Incentive, Conference, and Exhibition (MICE)

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Abstract

Online learning has been one of crucial topic in the Covid-19 pandemic era. This paper aims to describe the student's perception on the use of YouTube application as online learning media. This research used a descriptive qualitative approach by using questionnaire and interview. The class of this study was twenty-three students. The questionnaire was analyzed by using Likert-Scale and the interview was analyzed qualitatively. The interview script presented to get students statements about their perceptions of English for MICE online learning via YouTube, whether in positive or negative. The result of this research shows that using YouTube as English for MICE's online learning media gives many positive effects to the student's English mastery, such as vocabularies, practices and also increased of their English four skills. However, mostly students had trouble about lacks of internet connection, but this problem obviously solved well by them.

Keywords: Online learning, YouTube, MICE, English Department of State Polytechnic of Malang.

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Introduction

Regarding to the Covid-19 pandemic, which is changing all of living system in Indonesia to be conducted without having direct socialization, Ministry of Education and Culture of Indonesia released circular letter about policy of conducting online learning. It should be conducted as long as the Covid-19 pandemic occurs in order to prevent the spread of this dangerous virus. Policy of online learning is used for all of education level in Indonesia, right from kindergarten, elementary, junior, senior or even college or university.

Implementation of online learning cannot be separated from the use of many online learning media that used to replace media in the non-online learning (Aprianto, 2020; Nofrika, 2019). Based on that argument, it can be concluded that online learning always use technology as an online media. YouTube is one of them. YouTube is popular flat-form for

internet users especially who are willing to watch, upload or even download videos (Adisti, 2022; Anugerah et al., 2019; Cahyana, 2020; Jailani, 2022). Based on that argument, it can be concluded that YouTube is popular website in all generation in this world. This platform provided many features in which people could share video and get many responses from unlimited number and also limitless distance. However, this platform is not only presenting videos about music, movie, sport, and so on, but also having education matters (Dabamona & Yunus, 2021; Nasution, 2019; Nurmala Sari, 2019; Tahmina, 2023). Based on that argument, it can be concluded that YouTube has important role as media learning for education.

Due to all of the provided features and kinds, YouTube creates possibilities to be used as online learning media in some certain online learning without lowering the learning purposes. YouTube also used as learning platform (Putra & Suharto, 2022; Suharto, 2022; Zubaidi et al., 2021). Based on that argument, it is believed that most of the people in the all ages have a YouTube account, so that they use it to learn something. Therefore, YouTube is one of the most famous application for everyone (Ikhlasa & Suryadi, 2022; Putri, 2019; Wahyuningsih & Ni'mah, 2023). From that argument, YouTube is an easy application for everyone.

Regarding to the positive effect of using YouTube as online learning media, English Department in State Polytechnic of Malang decided to use this media for English for MICE class. English for MICE (Meeting, Incentives, Conventions and Exhibition) can be defined as activity of learning English in the tourism sector that is consisted of business events and activities (Qamariah et al., 2019; Smagina, 2017). Based on that argument, it can be concluded that MICE include activities that consisted of leisure and also business.

There are five previous research which examine YouTube as learning media (Abdullah et al., 2023; Fitriyani et al., 2023; Lestari et al., 2023; Nuriyah et al., 2023; Widiantari et al., 2023). Abdullah et al., (2023) investigated the use of YouTube as learning media. Then, Fitriyani et al., (2023) examines YouTube as a learning media in writing narrative text. After that, Lestari et al., (2023) examines YouTube as learning media in listening comprehension. Nuriyah et al., (2023) examines YouTube as science learning. Then, Widiantari et al., (2023) examines YouTube as alternative learning media for bilingual young learners. All of previous researches examine YouTube as learning media, but rarely to the use of YouTube media in English for MICE online learning. Regarding to this, the article concern was investigating students' perception on the use of YouTube over its use as online learning media in English for MICE class.

A few research focused on how the implications to students toward YouTube as a

platform in learning English. There have been limited studies concerned on their perceptions to use it. Therefore, this research intends to find them in this research. The objectives of this research are how many students access YouTube, how usefulness the YouTube platform to students, and to see how the students assume YouTube as a media in learning English.

Research Method

This research used descriptive qualitative approach by using questionnaire and interview. Qualitative study additionally involves such a method as observation activity through experimental natural setting. The class of this study was 23 students of English Department, State Polytechnic of Malang at English for MICE class. The questionnaire was analyzed by using Likert-scale and the interview was analyzed qualitatively. The questionnaire used in this research was divided into two parts, YouTube accessibility and YouTube usefulness. The interview script presented to get students statements about their perceptions of English for MICE's online learning via YouTube, whether in positive or negative. The interview result is also displayed in form of percentage to make easy the data conclusion.

Result and Discussion

The students fill the questionnaire to answer several questions. These questions related to the students' perceptions of YouTube accessibility. These results can be seen in the Table 1.

Table 1: Percentage of YouTube Accessibility

No.	Statements	Students response				
		VA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	VD (%)
1.	I have a YouTube account in my smart-phone	100	0	0	0	0
2.	I access YouTube everyday	90	10	0	0	0
3.	I don't have problem to access YouTube	10	0	0	75	15
4.	I use Wi-Fi to access YouTube	80	10	0	5	5
5.	I have internet connection in my house	5	0	0	5	90
6.	I am able to access YouTube every time and everywhere	80	10	0	5	5
Total		365	30	0	90	115
Average		66	5	0	15	19

From the table, it can be seen that 100% students have YouTube account which means that they were able to access YouTube everyday (90%) and easily access it every time and everywhere (80%). 80% of them were using Wi-Fi to access YouTube. However, they

had problems in the accessing YouTube due to the internet connection they did not have in their house (90%).

After that, students fill the second questionnaire. That questionnaire refers to the result of students' perception on YouTube usefulness can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Percentage of YouTube Usefulness

No.	Statements	Students' Responses				
		VA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	VD (%)
1.	I access YouTube to learn MICE class	90	10	0	0	0
2.	I get MICE class materials on YouTube	90	10	0	0	0
3.	I learn MICE vocabularies on YouTube	80	20	0	0	0
4.	I study MICE practice on YouTube	80	10	0	5	5
5.	I understand YouTube has contributed to MICE online learning	90	0	0	10	0
6.	I get positive impacts on MICE online learning via YouTube	80	10	0	5	5
TOTAL		510	60	0	20	10
Average		85	6	0	3	2

Based on Table 2, 90% students were accessing YouTube to learn about English for MICE. They gained English for MICE class materials (90%), including the vocabularies and practice (80%). At least, the students found that by using YouTube in the online learning. English for MICE class can be learnt well (90%). However, YouTube gives positive impacts to the students in the English for MICE's online learning (80%).

The use of YouTube as MICE online learning media is useful for the students as they can use it as references to be example or even to do assignment. However, they can also get positive impacts such as understanding of respect each other. YouTube which is able to give explanation completely towards audio visual can delivered purpose on point means that the students are able to understand the materials of the learning. Most of students agreed that learning towards video uploaded in the YouTube give them great references to do their task or assignment.

The interview conducted to give more explanation about the use of YouTube. There are several question and answer related with students' perception in using YouTube as learning media.

Table 3: List of Interview Questions

No.	Questions
1.	Do you think that using YouTube for online learning is useful you are your education nowadays?
2.	Do you think that using YouTube for English for MICE online learning has

	influenced your learning? Explain it!
3.	By using YouTube in the English for MICE online learning, do you think that your English mastery in this class has influenced positively?
4.	By using YouTube in the English for MICE online learning, do you get difficulties in the learning process?
5.	After this, what is your suggestion for next English for MICE class online learning?

Based on Table 3, in the first question 90% of the students explained that YouTube is most suitable media for online learning. They said that besides others online learning media, in which the learning commonly done by teacher-centered learning due to the limitation of the online learning media features, here in the learning by using YouTube application could give them more explanation through videos. The students stated that most of their online learning is just conducted by lecturing through kind of video call application where they could not get responsive idea to the learning activity but watching their lecturer giving explanation and showing power point. These 90% students found out that YouTube in which able to show them videos completed by features of comments from wider area gives them more enjoyable and acceptable online learning.

Then, In the second question, 85% of the students said that conducting English for MICE's online learning by using YouTube was fit to their necessity as English for MICE learners. YouTube which is suitable to be accessed everywhere created good condition for online learning. However, most of them stated that learning English for MICE class as online towards YouTube application is a good choice, in which it has to present lot of visualizations that cannot be done as face-to-face learning, such as presentation of meeting activity, incentive activity, convention activity and exhibition activity. In this case, the students were focused to describe how they feel towards learning English for MICE by using YouTube application and they stated that YouTube might be one of best platform used for this online learning due to the feature inside that is providing real conditions in form of video for the learners. So that, the learners could easily learn the English for MICE without having off-line learning in the classroom.

In the third question, 90% of the students showed positive answer about how using YouTube influenced their English mastery in the English for MICE class. English for MICE can be concluded as class in English learning area which needs practice more than learning activity in the classroom. YouTube as learning media for this class which is delivered in form of video increased the student's English mastery in many subjects. Through the video, the students directly learn about listening and also speaking including the pronunciation and the vocabularies used inside. Video could be one of good learning media where they also

stimulated well to write and read. As one of the examples, YouTube MICE video which discussed about *meeting* has given clear explanation about the materials to the students. By watching the video, the students could obviously find out how is *meeting* activity in the MICE context. They also studied about how to conduct the activity well, how to solve problem in the activity and what should they do as part of the activity. The most important is YouTube video influenced their English mastery in the English for MICE class.

Based on the fourth questions, mostly student right in the average of 90% stated that they get problem due to lacks of internet connections in their place. These students obviously explained that they enjoy the online learning from YouTube because they get many positive aspects from the use of YouTube especially in the English for MICE online learning, but they did not have Wi-Fi in their house. This problem created difficulties among their learning process. However, they still could find the solution such as asking Wi-Fi from their neighbors, friends or families. 10% of the students who answered that they had no difficulties in the learning showed that they already have Wi-Fi or good internet connection in their house.

Based on the fifth question, mostly students in the average 85% suggested that for the next English for MICE's online learning, the students should get chance to do task in form of video and upload it in their YouTube account to. They said that they want to get more views so that their English mastery can be reviewed well by many other people in the wider area. In addition, students need to do practice to learn this class. Either way, creating video and uploading it in the YouTube might be the best idea that can improve student's English mastery in the MICE class.

The result of this research shows that using YouTube as English for MICE's online learning media gives many positive effects to the student's English mastery in the English for MICE class, such as vocabularies, practices and also increased of their English four skills. However, mostly students experienced difficulties about lacks of internet connection, but this problem obviously solved well by them.

This current research is different from previous research conducted by Abdullah et al., (2023); Fitriyani et al., (2023); Lestari et al., (2023); Nuriyah et al., (2023); Widiantari et al., (2023). All of previous research uses YouTube for learning media not for English for MICE. This current research focused on YouTube as online media for English for MICE.

Conclusion

From the finding above, it could be concluded that the students consider using YouTube in the online learning of English for MICE class increased their English skill in the class. The students could learn about the materials better includes the specific vocabularies and practice of English for MICE. The students also consider that YouTube is the best choice learning media for English for MICE's online learning. The students also give suggestion that for the next English for MICE's online learning, the students should get chance to do task in form of video and upload it in their YouTube account to. However, mostly students experienced difficulties about lacks of internet connection, but this problem obviously solved well by them.

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